

JOHASAM: Journal of Health, Applied Sciences and Management
ISSN: 1597-7085, ISSN (Online): 2756-5343

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5747066

Volume 5 | Issue 2 | 2021

**ENVIRONMENTALLY-INDUCED DISEASES ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC WELL-BEING
OF A RURAL POPULACE IN EMOHUA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA IN RIVERS
STATE**

Ngozi Dennis Willy

School of Community Health

Rivers State College of Health Science and Management Technology

Port Harcourt

&

Kingsley Nyeghandah Onyekwere

School of Community Health

Rivers State College of Health Science and Management Technology

Port Harcourt

Abstract

This study investigated the environmentally-induced diseases on the socio-economic well-being of selected communities in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. It adopted the use of survey research design. Data were collected through the use of questionnaire which was administered in 14 randomly selected communities in the LGA. Two research questions, and one hypothesis guided the study. Mean and simple percentages were used to analyze the research questions, while the hypothesis was analysed with t-test statistic. Investigations revealed that the commonest environmentally-induced diseases in the area include cholera, diarrhea, chicken pox, influenza, measles, hepatitis A and E, foot rot, and vascular wilts. Although the emergence of the diseases may pose some threat on the socio-economic life of the people, statistically speaking, the diseases do not pose any significant effect on the people of the area. Arising from these findings, the researcher concluded by recommending for adequate public enlightenment campaign to educate the people on the importance of good environmental sanitation practices, frequent fumigation of surroundings, establishment of more functional healthcare facilities, among others

© 2021 Rivers State College of Health Science & Management Technology
<https://www.rschst.edu.ng/journals>